

Derivatives of 1-Hydroxy-2-naphthoic Acid. Part I.

4-Halogeno-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic Acid and their Derivatives.

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Since much work has been done in these laboratories on derivatives of salicylic acid, it was thought interesting to examine the reactions of 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid, which can be regarded as a salicylic acid with the 3- and 4- positions fused with a benzene molecule. Thus, its behaviour may be analogous with the 3-substituted derivatives of salicylic acid, since the position 4 does not play an important rôle, being outside the directing influences.

Thus, the acid chloride of the naphthoic acid is as easily obtained (Anschutz and co-workers, *Annalen*, 1906, **346**, 361) as that of *o*-cresotic acid or salicylic acid with the 3- position occupied, either by chloro, nitro (Anschutz, *Ber.*, 1897, **30**, 222; *Annalen*, 1906, **346**, 342, 336), or bromo group (Hirwe, *unpublished work*). The esters of the 3-substituted salicylic acids are obtained through the silver salts or through the acid chlorides (Anschutz and Anspach, *Annalen*, 1906, **346**, 313; Hübner, *ibid.*, 1879, **195**, 34; Anschutz and co-workers, *ibid.*, 1906, **346**, 343). With the naphthoic acid it has been found very difficult to get the ester directly (Kauffmann and Egner, *Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 3782).

To extend the above analogies further, the naphthoic acid was halogenated and the behaviour of these acids studied. These halogeno acids were obtained by the substitution of the sulphonic acid group in 4-sulpho-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid (Konig, *Ber.*, 1889, **22**, 787; 1890, **23**, 806) by the halogens and the halogen-free phthalic acid, obtained on oxidation of these acids, further confirms their structures.

The 4-halogenonaphthoic acids gave the naphthoyl chloride with phosphorus pentachloride as easily as the 3:5-disubstituted salicylic acids (Anschutz, *loc. cit.*).

Various derivatives of these acids have been described. The work is being extended.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Bromo-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic Acid.—Bromine (2.5 g.) in acetic acid (10 c.c.) was gradually added in the cold to 4-sulpho-1-hydroxy-

2-naphthoic acid (5 g.) suspended in acetic acid (50 c.c.) and the mixture then heated at 100° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour to complete the reaction. The bromo-acid (3.6 g.) crystallised from acetic acid in white needles, m.p. 240-41° (decomp.), mixed m.p. with the acid prepared according to Weil (*Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 3060; *cf.* Schmitt and Burkard, *Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 2700). (Found: Br, 30.1. Calc. for $C_{11}H_7O_3Br$: Br, 30.0 per cent).

Phthalic acid (m.p. 197°) was obtained, when the bromo acid (2 g.) was heated with nitric acid (*d* 1.16, 15 c.c.) in a sealed tube at 150-60° for 8 hours.

4-Bromo-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoyl Chloride.—A mixture of the above acid (3 g.), dry benzene (4 c.c.), dry light petroleum ether (10 c.c.) and phosphorus pentachloride (3 g.) was gently heated on the water-bath, until a clear yellow solution was obtained. The naphthoyl chloride separated on cooling as yellow needles, which were collected and washed with dry light petroleum ether and dried over phosphorus pentoxide, m.p. 118-9°. [Found: Total halogen calc. as Cl, 28.5; by analysis of silver halides Cl, 12.4; Br, 27.8. $C_{11}H_6O_2BrCl$ requires Cl, 12.4; Br, 28.0 per cent].

4-Chloro-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic Acid.—Dry chlorine gas (1 g.) was passed at 65°, with constant stirring, through 4-sulpho-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid (5 g.) suspended in acetic acid (25 c.c.). The solid (1.4 g.) crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles, m.p. 232-33° (decomp.), mixed m.p. with the acid prepared according to Reissert (*Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 866; *cf.* Weil and Heerdt, *Ber.*, 1922, **55**, 288; Weil, *Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 3061). (Found: Cl, 15.9. Calc. for $C_{11}H_7O_3Cl$: Cl, 16.0 per cent).

On oxidation of the acid, in the same way as in the case of 4-bromo-acid, phthalic acid was obtained.

4-Chloro-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoyl Chloride was prepared in the same way as its bromo isomer in fine yellow needles, m.p. 121-22°. (Found: Cl, 29.4. $C_{11}H_6O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 29.5 per cent).

The phenyl and β -naphthyl esters of these halogeno-acids were prepared by heating a mixture of the acid with the respective phenol and phosphorus oxychloride at 140-150° to a clear solution and then treating with water. Alkyl esters were obtained by heating either the silver salt of the acid or the naphthoyl chloride with the respective alkyl iodide or alcohol. The arylamides were prepared by treating the benzene solution of the naphthoyl chloride with the respective amine.

TABLE I.
Derivatives of 4-Bromo-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic Acid.

Name.	Formula.	Crystallised from.	Appearance.	M.p.	Found.	Analysis.	Calc.
Sodium salt	$C_{11}H_6O_3BrNa \cdot 2\frac{1}{2} H_2O$	Water	Shining needles		Na, 6.9% H ₂ O, 13.8		6.9% 13.5
Potassium salt	$C_{11}H_6O_3BrK$	"	Pinkish needles		K, 12.7		12.8
Phenyl ester	$C_{17}H_{11}O_3Br$	Acetone and alcohol	Shining needles	104.5°	Br, 23.3		23.3
<i>β</i> -Naphthyl ester	$C_{21}H_{15}O_3Br$	Acetic acid	Long white needles	183-84°	20.4		20.1
Methyl ester	$C_{12}H_8O_3Br$	Alcohol	Small white needles	122-22°	28.2		28.5
Ethyl ester	$C_{13}H_{11}O_3Br$	"	Grey needles	86-87°	27.2		27.1
Amide	$C_{17}H_{13}O_2NBr$	"	White needles	164-65°	23.1		23.4
<i>o</i> -Toluidide	$C_{18}H_{14}O_2NBr$	"	" "	164-65°	22.8		22.5
<i>m</i> -Toluidide	"	Acetone and alcohol	Pinkish white needles	202.3°	22.6		22.5
<i>p</i> -Toluidide	"	"	White needles	150-51°	22.8		22.5

TABLE II.
Derivatives of 4-Chloro-1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic Acid.

Name.	Formula.	Crystallised from.	Appearance.	M. P.	Found.	Analysis. Req.
Potassium salt	$C_{11}H_6O_3ClK$	Water	Grey needles		K, 14.8%	15.0%
Phenyl ester	$C_{17}H_{11}O_3Cl$	Acetone and alcohol	Pale yellow plates	103.4°	Cl, 11.9	11.9
β -Naphthyl ester	$C_{21}H_{13}O_3Cl$	Acetic acid	White needles	186.87°	9.9	10.2
Methyl ester	$C_{12}H_{10}O_3Cl$	Alcohol	" "	120.21°	15.0	15.0
Ethyl ester	$C_{13}H_{11}O_3Cl$	"	Grey needles	92.93°	14.2	14.2
Anilide	$C_{17}H_{10}O_2NCl$	"	White needles	180.81°	Cl, 12.1 N(micro), 4.6	12.0 4.7
<i>o</i> -Toluidide	$C_{18}H_{14}O_2NCl$	Acetic acid	" "	148.49°	Cl, 11.3	11.4
<i>m</i> -Toluidide	"	"	Pale yellow needles	188.89°	11.6	11.4
<i>p</i> -Toluidide	"	"	Shining grey needles	143.44°	11.2	11.4

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